

MUCOLIZATION OF LATERAL DEFECTS LINED WITH BUCCAL FAT PAD IN CLEFT PALATE REPAIR

Shaeva R.G.

Self-appointed co-researcher

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery
Tashkent State Dental Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Shomurodov K.E.

Professor, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery
Tashkent State Dental Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Annotation. Despite the existence of more than 300 surgical methods for the treatment of congenital cleft palate (CCP), the treatment of such children remains among the important tasks of medicine due to developing postoperative complications and the need for additional interventions to correct unsatisfactory results .

The aim of the study was a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the use of buccal fat pad (BFP) to cover the area of lateral defects in the surgical treatment of congenital cleft palate.

An open prospective randomized study included 103 children aged one to 5 years with congenital cleft lip and palate (CCLP), registered at the dispensary in the Department of Pediatric maxillofacial surgery of TSDI. The largest percentage of children with CCLP were boys – 64 (62.1%), girls – 39 (37.9%). According to the severity of the defect, 32 (31.1%) had UCLP, 36 (34.9%) had bilateral CCLP, and 35 (34%) had isolated CCP.

Depending on the severity of the congenital malformation of the upper lip and palate in children, operations were performed at the following time depending on age: 1) cheiloplasty – from 6 to 8 months; 2) veloplasty – from 8 months to 1.2 years; 3) palatoplasty – at the age of 1.6 to 5 years. All children underwent a clinical examination before surgery, including a general clinical blood and urine test, a biochemical blood test for total protein, protein fractions, enzymes, residual nitrogen, urea, bilirubin, electrolytes, if necessary, chest X-ray and ECG. In addition, the children were consulted by a pediatrician, an anesthesiologist, an orthodontist, an otolaryngologist and a neurologist if necessary.

The largest number of children – 37 (35.9%) people – were operated on using the Frolova L.E. method. 35 (34%) children were operated on using Azimov M.I. method – transverse dissection of the soft palate, with longitudinal suturing of the wound, amounted to Bardach J. uranoplasty was performed in 31 (30.1%) children. Depending on the method of coating (material) of lateral defects, each group of subjects was divided into subgroups by random distribution: a – iodoform (n=25), b – PRF (n=27), c – collagen sponge (CS) (n=25), d – BFP (n=26).

PRF was obtained by centrifugation of 30 ml of venous blood in dry glass vacuum tubes (3000 rpm, 10 min). PRF was extracted from the test tube with sterile forceps and separated from the adjacent layer of red blood cells. PRF was maintained with a gauze swab for 5 days after surgery.

Postoperative follow-up was performed at the 1st, 2nd and 3rd weeks after plastic surgery, which included a clinical assessment of the area of palate plastic surgery and examination of patients. To assess the rate of epithelialization of the wound, a 3% H₂O₂ was used, which

interacts with connective tissue catalase to form bubbles. Conversely, bubbles do not form if the epithelium covers the wound surface [5]. The degree of epithelialization was assessed on the 7th, 14th, 21st and 28th days after surgery. The results were indicated as 0, 1/3, 2/3, 1 for each area of the wound.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics for Windows (IBM, Armonk, New York). Stratification was performed based on the frequency of postoperative complications using the Chi-squared criterion, and p less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The greatest number of complications was noted in the group of patients who had iodoform applied to cover the wound surface in the area of lateral defects. There was an accumulation of food, which was the cause of bad breath, the development of the inflammatory process (5 (20%)), which in turn prevented the epithelialization of the surgical wound and in some cases required additional surgical intervention. Rough scarring was observed in 8 (32%) patients. The epithelialization process in this subgroup lasted on average 30 ± 3.5 days.

It should be noted that the collection of a sufficient amount of venous blood for PRF in most patients presented certain difficulties associated with the physiological characteristics of childhood. There was also a discrepancy between the obtained volume of PRF and the parameters of the surgical wound in the area of lateral defects. The epithelialization process in this subgroup lasted on average 23 ± 1.3 days.

Using CS, 4 (16%) patients had suture divergence and, as a result, material loss from the surface of the defect. It was also difficult to obtain a material with the appropriate parameters to fully cover the area of lateral defects. The epithelialization process in this subgroup lasted on average 22 ± 2.2 days.

Conclusions: Thus, buccal fat pad is the optimal source of vascularized tissue to cover the area of lateral defects in the surgical treatment of CCP. The simplicity of mobilization, minimal traumatization and accessibility of the method determine the prospects of this method. The rate of epithelialization and wound healing is higher compared to the traditional method (iodoform), the use of collagen sponge and PRF with minimal risk of complications.

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